

Summit Report: Boston-Area Complex Risk Science

Exploring New Frontiers and a New Community for Understanding Risk

Held June 9, 2025 | Hosted by NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory & Northeastern University

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Introduction

This report reflects and extends the energy and inquiry of the June 2025 summit convened to challenge traditional boundaries in risk science and explore how complexity and social science can open new paradigms of resilience. Our ambition is to help a nascent community cohere, pursue pressing questions, and organize into self-directed clusters to carry the work forward.

Description

On June 9, 2025, we hosted a one-day summit in Boston hosted by the NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory and Northeastern University for a cross-disciplinary group of thinkers and doers working on risk, resilience, social systems, and complexity.

“ Our goal: to identify non-obvious gaps in risk science, particularly around multi-hazard interactions, cascading consequences, and vulnerability, and to explore how complexity science and social science can help us understand and address them. ”

We exist in a world of interdependent systems [[Helbing, 2013](#)] whose entanglement gives rise to difficult to quantify vulnerabilities [[Vespignani, 2010](#)] and extreme uncertainties that make their deterministic management impossible. The interdependence of our 21st century world is not merely economic nor solely technological, but extends into the social realm as well [[Beck and Ritter, 1992](#)]. Complexity science as a paradigm of scientific discovery (e.g., [McGranaghan; \[2024\]](#)) has produced a profound shift in scientific thought and concomitant understanding, perhaps most effective in its ability to evolve scientific disciplines toward new foci.

The topic of risk in natural hazards and ecological science remains in its infancy, as are attempts to connect the study of purely physical systems with socio-physical systems. Our modern world requires a more robust science of risk and complexity calls us to a new epistemological engagement: from risk to resilience. An articulated and practicable risk science and resilience paradigm is the principle pathway to the advancement of science to address global (at once intimate and planetary) crises.

As evidenced by climbing temperatures and warming targets, growing social and economic inequality, rising precarity of critical societal infrastructure, and persistent selection for the immediate over the long-term, the ways we have been doing and sharing science have failed to grow to the immensity of challenges in the 21st century. A new science, by which has always meant a new way of doing science, is imperative and, with a new paradigm of risk and resilience, possible.

Socio-ecological-technological systems (SETS) are the frontier of this paradigm of complex risk and resilience science. We will convene a unique group—unlikely to come together elsewhere—to explore bold yet feasible questions that define this cross-disciplinary, cross-domain community and illuminate the new projects needed to address them.

Key Themes and 'Dialectics' that open new space for their exploration

This section reveals fertile ground for sustaining interactions. We use the ']' notation for the dialectics gesturing toward the fact that these items are often positioned as opposites/contradictions and that placing them into conversation will reveal space where before there was only a boundary.

A goal of this section is to articulate 'analysis working groups' that might organize around the key theme and embrace the dialectics that help open new space for those themes that respond to the challenges and gaps we identified during the Summit.

A. Tipping Points and System Memory

Guiding Questions:

- How do we detect proximity to tipping points across scales?
- What are suitable metrics of chronic vs. acute exposure?
- How might 'breathing room' (time periods of reprieve from a given hazard condition) be an aspect of a system's resilience?

Dialectics:

- *Perturbation-based resilience testing | Natural rhythm-based indicators*
- *Extreme event rarity | Cumulative, unseen stressors*

Working Group:

WG1: Indicators of Systemic Fragility

Tasked with developing shared, interpretable, and possibly set-theoretic measures of system fragility and recovery.

B. Situated Risk and Contextual Vulnerability

Guiding Questions:

- How do we capture what is meaningful and vulnerable in place-specific contexts?
- What are the literacies needed to translate across technical, institutional, and social boundaries?

Dialectics:

- *Bespokeness | Generality*
- *Ethnographic | Data-driven*

Working Group:

WG2: Context-Aware Risk Metrics

Focusing on hybrid methodologies (qualitative + quantitative) to define and measure vulnerability in ways communities recognize as legitimate, find actionable, and trust.

C. Complexity Science as Method and Ethos

Guiding Questions:

- What does it mean to “hold the complexity with integrity”?
- What tools do we need to preserve texture rather than collapse it?

Dialectics:

- *Reduction | Complexity | Contextuality*
- *Modeling simplification | Methodological pluralism*

Working Group:

WG3: Complexity Methodologies for Risk

To chart, compare, and co-develop new complexity-informed risk science tools, including ensemble methods, recovery rate metrics, and participatory modeling.

D. Infrastructure Entanglement and Multi-Hazard Dynamics

Guiding Questions:

- What datasets are needed to model cascading infrastructure risks?
- How can we responsibly model interdependencies like power-telecom systems?
- How might we explore multi-hazards when the intersection of hazards makes the historical record even less adequate and when it is infeasible to merely create joint probabilities of all of the variables?

Dialectics:

- *Isolated hazard models | Multi-hazard quantification*
- *Assumption of system modularity | Interdependent system simulations*
- *Single-point failure | Distributed adaptation*

Working Group:

WG4: Cascading Risk and Interconnected Infrastructure

To gather data, simulate scenarios, and create modular models that reflect real-world coupling (e.g., power grid | communications | water). Map multi-actor spaces as connected to infrastructures and hazards that act to create risk to those spaces.

E. Aligning Decisions with the Timescales and Uncertainties of Risk

Guiding Questions:

- How do we model decisions under deep uncertainty?
- What is the appropriate temporal scale for resilience modeling and planning? How do these expand across temporal scales?
- How do short-term decisions shape long-term risk—and vice versa?

Dialectics:

- *Past-performance-based forecasting (past predicts future) | Narrative scenario construction (non-ergodicity)*
- *Deterministic action | Probabilistic awareness*

“Temporal depth” refers to the timescales over which decisions, risks, or system dynamics unfold and become visible—past, present, near future, and deep future. It speaks to how short-term thinking can miss long-term risks, or how our models may fail if they don’t account for the fact that hazards, vulnerabilities, and decisions interact across time horizons.

Participants reflected on how many of our tools and institutions are tuned to short-term signals, yet the challenges we face—climate change, infrastructure resilience, socio-political risk—unfold over years or decades. There was also a shared recognition that different groups (e.g., utilities, planners, communities) operate with different time scales, which can cause disconnects in coordination.

Working Group:

WG5: Timescales, Narratives, and Decision Horizons

This group will explore how to design modeling tools, planning processes, and communication strategies that reflect the real-world timing of risk and resilience, including narrative-based approaches and methods for bridging short- and long-term thinking; especially in situations of deep or extreme uncertainty.

F. Learning from What Went Right

Guiding Questions:

- How do we capture what *went right* in system stress events?
- Can we develop new post-event analysis methods that focus on protective factors, not just failures? How do we systematically capture actions or conditions that helped systems absorb or adapt to stress?
- Can this become a basis for “self-supervised learning” in infrastructure systems? (e.g., addressing the dearth of observations of extremes by understanding ‘positive resilience’ through the much more abundant observations of what went right)

Dialectics:

- *Failure analysis | Resilience enactment*
- *Reconstruction of past events | Modeling adaptive reorganization*

Participants expressed a desire to study successful system responses—moments of resilience, adaptation, or protection—during crises. This shift from failure analysis to “what went right” opens a new class of empirical events to study and makes room for learning from real-world, lived examples of resilience.

Working Group:

WG6: Post-Event Protective Actions and Success Mapping

This group will design methods to study and document how individuals, institutions, or system dynamics protected infrastructure or communities during adverse events, and identify mechanisms worth sustaining or scaling.

Emerging Community Organizing Principles

- **Start with inquiry:** Let questions, not categories, lead.
- **Cultivate pluralism:** Accept multiple epistemologies and disciplines.
- **Support early-career researchers:** Anchor sustainability in continuity.
- **Focus on science from conversational, dialectical approach:** Frame research in terms of the space it opens between traditionally opposing ideas.
- **Embed co-creation:** Data, methods, and priorities must include community partners.
- **Fractal gathering:** Maintain continuity of this group across future opportunities to gather and pick up the ideas from this event in those settings.

Participants discussed how to sustain interactions and an idea of ‘fractal gathering’ was articulated in which we have continuity of this core community across events that will occur in the future of various scale sizes (perhaps sessions organized at major conferences or serendipitous side meetings associated with them; smaller workshops held at our institutions and in major cities we are each from; seminar series; all the way up to funded multi-day workshops and hosted conferences).

Recommended Resources

Papers & Reports

- De Angeli et al. (2022) – *Multi-hazard spatial-temporal impact framework*
- Helbing (2013) – *Globally networked risks and complexity*
- Hochrainer-Stigler et al. (2023) – *Toward systemic multi-hazard assessment*
- Constantino & Weber (2021) – *Narratives in deep uncertainty and decision-making*

Data & Tools

- [Regional Energy Shortfall Threshold \(REST\)](#) metric
 - [NAERM](#)
 - Sai Ravela's coherent random field mixtures and alternatives to digital twins
 - [EPRI & ISO NE's Climate READi initiative](#)
 - Open repository [an organized \(and living\) list](#) of relevant resources for multi-hazards, complex risk, and resiliency; open to curation by summit organizers
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Next Steps and Opportunities

Forming Analysis Working Groups

We recommend self-organization by shared question, with summit attendees encouraged to:

- Select a theme-aligned WG
- Nominate a convenor
- Identify 1–2 shared datasets or case studies
- Reconvene in 90 days for a virtual follow-up

Proposed Outputs

- Short WG memos outlining methods, gaps, and collaboration opportunities
 - Shared concept maps of risk/resilience dimensions
 - Open-access working papers or web-based artifacts to attract new collaborators
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Final Reflections

As one participant asked: “What would a *risk commons* look like?”

This summit may be the first sketch. It revealed a community ready to translate complexity into meaningful, shared structures for inquiry. What comes next depends on what we choose to build together.

Let this be a *beginning* rather than a *conclusion*.

Appendix A: Agenda

9:00 am

Meeting & Coffee

9:15 am

Complex Risk: A paradigm of resilience and framing a new collective

Ryan McGranaghan

Data Scientist and Research Scientist, NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory

9:45 am

Sustainability, data science, and experiential AI for resilient systems

10:00 am

Keynote

Qi "Ryan" Wang

Associate Professor and Vice Chair for Research, Civil and Environmental Engineering, Northeastern University

10:45 am

Discussion & Collaborative Project Idea Generation

11:15 am

Break

11:45 am

Keynote

Lynée Turek-Hankins

Postdoctoral Fellow, Dartmouth College

12:30 pm

Lunch

2:00 pm

Panel: Power grid as a demonstrative system for a complex risk and resilience paradigm

Nicholas Judson

Associate Leader - Energy Systems Group, MIT Lincoln Laboratory

Galen Nelson

Chief Climate Officer, Massachusetts Clean Energy Center (MassCEC)

Jinye Zhao

Principal Energy Market Analyst, ISO New England

Andrea Staid

Principal Technical Leader in the Energy Systems and Climate Analysis Group, EPRI

3:00 pm

Keynote

Sai Ravela

Principal Research Scientist, Earth, Atmospheric and Planetary Sciences (EAPS), MIT Center for Computational Science & Engineering

3:45 pm

Discussion & Collaborative Project Idea Generation

3:45 pm

Discussion & Collaborative Project Idea Generation

4:15 pm

Collaborative Working & Artifact Creation

5:00 pm

Adjourn

Appendix B: Participants

Individual	Institution
Ryan McGranaghan	NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology
Auroop Ganguly	Northeastern University

Sai Ravela	MIT
Lynée Turek-Hankins	Dartmouth
Qi "Ryan" Wang	Northeastern University
Jack Watson	Northeastern University
Aayushi Mishra	Northeastern University
Puja Das	Northeastern University
Dave Raviraj	Northeastern University
Danish Mansoor	Northeastern University
Dian Indrawati	Northeastern University
Diyali Goswami	Northeastern University
Orijeet Mukherjee	Northeastern University
Galen Nelson	Mass CEC
Paul Kirshen	UMass Boston
Jinye Zhao	ISO NE
Wilson Rickerson	Converge Strategies
Andrea Staid	EPRI
Jennifer Morris	MIT
Thomas Vandal	Zeus AI
Dan Braha	University of Massachusetts, Dartmouth
Rufai Omowunmi Balogun	Clark University
Mette Böll	MIT
Liana Bernt	NASA Lifelines Fellow; NU
Mauricio Santillana	NU
Ana Trisovic	MIT; Harvard
Heather Zwahlen	MIT Lincoln Lab
Jonathan Pitts	MIT Lincoln Lab
Natasha Krell	MIT Lincoln Lab
Patrick Reed	Multisector Dynamics CoP; Cornell
Jonathan Lamontagne	Tufts University

Vivek Srikrishnan	Cornell University
Stan Heckman	Whisker Labs
Julia Hopkins	MIT Lincoln Lab
Nicholas Judson	MIT Lincoln Lab
Stefano Galelli	Cornell University
Annie Weathers	MIT Lincoln Lab